

Enhancing Security in Industry 4.0 / 5.0 Data Sharing: A Risk Modeling Approach

1st Alexandros Nizamis

*Department of Digital Industry Technologies
National and Kapodistrian University of Athens*
alnizami@dind.uoa.gr
Euboea, Greece

*and Information Technologies Institute
Centre for Research and Technology Hellas*
alnizami@iti.gr
Thessaloniki, Greece

2nd Nadia Masood Khan

*Digital Systems 4.0
Plovdiv, Bulgaria*
nadia@digisys4.eu

3rd Usman Wajid

*Information Catalyst
Valencia, Spain*
usman.wajid@informationcatalyst.com

4th Stefano Modafferi

*University of Southampton
Southampton, UK*
S.D.Modafferi@soton.ac.uk

5th Nikolay Mehandjiev

*Digital Systems 4.0
Plovdiv, Bulgaria*
nikolay@digisys4.eu

6th Konstantinos Votis

*Information Technologies Institute
Centre for Research and Technology Hellas*
Thessaloniki, Greece
kvotis@iti.gr

Abstract—Today, the advancement of Industries 4.0 and 5.0 has enabled the digital transformation of the manufacturing domain and the creation of data-sharing ecosystems. A cornerstone of this advancement is the Internet of Things, which has enabled the realization of applications related to real-time monitoring, automation, and analytics. However, IoT-enabled data sharing scenarios across organizations have also introduced significant security, privacy, and trust challenges. This paper presents the Security Risk Modeler (SRM), a tool designed to address these challenges by providing a systematic approach to identifying, analyzing, and mitigating security risks in Industry 4.0/5.0 data sharing environments. The tool is applied to a real-world industrial waste management scenario that involves IoT enabled waste bins, cloud-based analytics, and data sharing between two companies. Through this case study, SRM demonstrates its ability to model complex systems, identify threats, and propose actionable mitigation controls. Evaluations by industry stakeholders highlighted the tool’s usability, risk analysis capabilities, and potential for broader adoption in securing Industry 4.0/5.0 ecosystems.

Index Terms—Industry 4.0 and 5.0, cybersecurity, risk modeling, data sharing, threat mitigation

I. INTRODUCTION

Industries 4.0 & 5.0 [1] and the Internet of Things (IoT) [2] have revolutionized data sharing ecosystems, enabling the development of a wide series of applications such as real-time monitoring, automation, analytics, and decision-making. However, they have also introduced a series of challenges [3] related to security, privacy, and trust. The most common of these challenges [4], [5] are related to unauthorized access to sensitive industrial data, inconsistency in security policies between data-sharing partners, compliance risks and corresponding regulations.

The modeling of security risks can play a crucial role in the identification, analysis, and mitigation of security risks in Industry 4.0/5.0 data sharing ecosystems. Effective security controls and mitigation actions can be implemented, starting with a systematic assessment of threats and vulnerabilities. Several threats are connected with data sharing ecosystems such as data leakage, unauthorized access, non-compliance with regulations, and various operational risks. To identify, model and mitigate risks and threats, software [6] is used, with specific methodologies and applications in specific domains such as smart manufacturing [7]. These software and methodologies ensure that the necessary security controls are already considered and implemented in the system.

A series of methodologies are available related to the identification of threats such as STRIDE (Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of privilege) [8], [9] and STORE (Security Threat Oriented Requirements Engineering) [10]. In addition to threat identification methodologies, the authors in [11] have introduced a methodology that combines STRIDE with DREAD (Damage potential, Reproducibility, Exploitability, Affected users, and Discoverability) that enables the evaluation of security threats. In an approach to make a step forward from thread identification to simulation of possible scenarios, a threat modeling language for enterprise security is introduced [12] to provide attack simulations.

System Security Modeler (SSM) goes beyond the aforementioned methodologies by integrating system modeling and semantic reasoning. Not only identifies or scores threats, it also models the system and simulates risk based on those models. Hence, it provides end-to-end system risk modeling using

semantic models. A user can model any IT system, including users, devices and data flows, and SSM [13] will dynamically assess risks based on new threats or system changes based on information security risk management standards [25] and provides risk analysis. Moreover, it enables the propagation of causes and effects.

In the current work, a Security Risk Modeler (SRM) based on SSM [13] is introduced. The SRM tool was developed for the purposes of an EC-funded research project [15] and is designed to read machine-readable processing configurations and eliminates the construction of the system model by an expert, through which SRM can handle security risks when the system configuration changes and highlight any risks that arise from the new configuration. SRM modeling is done by first developing a conceptual mapping of system configuration to the SRM asset types which is then used by the tool for auto-developing and validating the system model. In the current study, it is applied to an Industry 4.0 scenario [17].

The scenario studied was related to the modeling and risk assessment of the data-sharing ecosystem for the management of industrial wastes. It included IoT devices, fog and cloud infrastructure to support IoT monitoring and data analytics applications [16]. The SRM allowed the modeling of the complete system, along with the identification and assessment of possible risks. Proposals for the mitigation of security risks were also provided. The outcome of the tool was evaluated by the companies' representatives to proceed with the risk assessment and mitigation. In this paper, an example report that presents the identified threats along with the mitigation applied or accepted is also presented.

Following the introductory section, the remainder of the paper is organized as follows. The Security Risk Modeler tool is introduced in Section 2. The Industry 4.0 scenario is presented in Section 3 along with the SRM application for security risk assessment. The results of the application of the SRM to the scenario are discussed in Section 4. Conclusions are available in Section 5.

II. SECURITY RISK MODELER (SRM)

A. SRM Overview and Main Functionalities

Security Risk Modeler (SRM) is a design-time risk assessment tool that checks for security threats and vulnerabilities in (distributed and integrated) ICT systems. It is based on the risk assessment approach of the International Organization for Standardization / International Electrotechnical Commission (ISO/IEC 27005) [31] [26] standard that defines best practices for the management of information security risks, with a special emphasis on the conformity to the standards of an Information Security Management System (ISMS).

SRM uses a domain knowledge base for the identification of threats, which is based on the ISO 27005 [31] risk assessment procedure and the Open Worldwide Application Security Project (OWASP) [32] for the security of the web application and checks compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [33] when personal data are processed.

SRM uses a structured, model-driven approach to encode its knowledge base, relying on domain ontologies and formal representations of security concepts aligning with ISO 27005's requirement for formal risk assessments. Assets are defined by their type, such as servers, sensors, or data stores, and include associated attributes. Threats are linked to these asset types based on known vulnerabilities, their underlying causes, and potential consequences. Interdependencies between assets are modeled through relational constructs such as "depends on," "connected to," and "trusts," capturing how components influence one another. The core modeling technique involves defining cause-and-effect chains that connect threat causes (e.g. weak authentication) to their effects (e.g., unauthorized access), along with possible mitigations or controls (e.g., two-factor authentication, firewall rules). These relationships are represented using directed graphs that simulate how attacks can propagate through a system. SRM automatically assigns consequences and their impact level for the assets in the system model following the ISO 27005 standard. Users / stakeholders must identify critical assets and set the impact level for the identified consequences.

The development of the SRM system model is carried out through the following steps:

Context Establishment

- Defining the operational environment, including the scope, objectives, and constraints of the system.
- Identify key stakeholders, their roles, and the interactions between them.

Asset Connectivity

- Mapping the relationships and dependencies between assets (e.g., networks, devices, users, data).
- Analyze how assets are interconnected to identify potential attack vectors.

Web of Attack Paths

- Evaluating possible attack routes that adversaries could exploit to compromise the system.
- Considering both direct and indirect paths that leverage interconnected assets.

Secondary Threats

- Identifying indirect or cascading threats that arise as a result of primary attacks.
- Assessing how vulnerabilities in one asset can impact others within the connected ecosystem.

By integrating these elements, the system provides a holistic view of security risks, allowing proactive mitigation strategies and enhanced resilience against complex threats.

Through the implementation of ISO standards, the SRM tool provides guidance for establishing, implementing, maintaining, and continuously improving the aspects of information security and privacy in ICT systems. The use of the SRM tool can enable companies in all sectors to become aware of cybersecurity risks and proactively identify and address security-related weaknesses in their systems.

B. SRM Architecture and Implementation

SRM builds upon the core implementation of SSM, extending it with automated system configuration parsing and validation capabilities. Therefore, the SRM architecture extends the SSM one. In particular, the SSM tool is a Java application that can be accessed through a Representational State Transfer – Application Programming Interface (REST-API) for client applications. The primary client application, which uses ReactJS, provides a web-based user interface. The Web UI provides a user-friendly interface for the security analyst to develop a system model by selecting the relevant asset types and their interconnections.

The access to services is managed by an external Keycloak [27] instance that authenticates users to access different parts of the SSM.

The internal architecture is shown in Fig. 1. SRM stores data in the following two databases:

- MongoDB [28], which stores authorization data about user access rights and model meta-data.
- JenaTDB [29] holds the knowledge base of threats, controls, and system models.

A user interacts with the web browser (ReactJS) and is authenticated via Keycloak. Spring security validates the Keycloak access token and provides access to the tool through a REST API. The user draws a model that describes their system in terms of the assets and relationships encoded in JenaDB. The system Models embedded in JenaDB contains patterns of assets of different types (e.g. ICT components, processes, data, stakeholders and physical spaces) and relationships, threats that pertain to these patterns, misbehaviours (adverse effects) that occur on the assets if the threats are able to affect the assets, and controls that can block the threats and thus mitigate the risks.

The Security Modeler matches asset patterns between model (created by the user) and system models (embedded in JenaDB), and from this identifies matching asset patterns and applicable threats, which determine adverse effects on assets. MongoDB stores model metadata and access control. In addition, the SSM adaptor (implemented in Python) is a separate microservice that can provide a risk analysis of an operational model.

Three new SRM services (extending SSM) have been developed to enhance conceptual mapping and simplify the handling of common modeling issues, such as filtering out known errors and recognizing previously implemented controls. The SRM Service accepts system configurations as input, allowing flexible model submission and supporting back-end functions for loading, validating, and calculating risks. Authentication and authorization have been strengthened through token-based access, ensuring that models are securely associated with individual user accounts to prevent unauthorized access (part of the Keycloak Service). Keycloak manages token issuance and secures back-end communication between services. The SRM Service also supports both synchronous and asynchronous requests, with secure delivery of concise risk analysis reports.

Fig. 1. Internal architecture of the SRM tool

The SRM Mapper Service automates the processing of system configurations, enabling advanced conceptual mapping and the handling of recurring modeling issues. It communicates directly with the SRM Service to validate models, perform risk calculations, and return summary reports based on request type. All interactions are secured via HTTPS and require token-based authentication for API access.

III. APPLYING SRM TO AN INDUSTRY 4.0 DATA SHARING SCENARIO

A. Industrial Waste Management: The KLEEMANN and ELDIA Use Case

The SRM tool was applied in a real-world scenario to provide a risk assessment for a data sharing system. The scenario includes two companies, KLEEMANN Hellas S.A. [18], a large lift manufacturer, and ELDIA S.A. [19], a greek waste management company as shown in Fig. 2. The application scenario includes a smart waste management solution for bins located in KLEEMANN's production premisses. The bins are equipped with IoT sensors that transmit bin fill level data over the Internet. The data becomes available to a cloud server where a data analytics platform is deployed to provide a visualization dashboard for bins fill level and analytics services about forecasts and estimations of bins collection date, etc. ELDIA operators access the data analytics platform, deployed on the cloud server, through a PC in their premisses. Then they use the available dashboard to monitor the bins fill level and use the available analytics to provide early planning for waste collection and optimal waste management services. The optimal collection of waste, such as scrap metal, is crucial for the manufacturing company, as full bins at the production site lead to production process delays as its secondary outcomes (wastes) cannot be handled, and production has to stop.

However, this integrated system for waste management includes a series of IoT devices, network devices, computers, and servers. It is also distributed in three different locations. The premises of the two companies and the location of the cloud server. In particular, the application scenario [17] includes:

Fig. 2. High-level architecture of KLEEMANN-ELDIA data sharing scenario

- IoT devices based on ultrasonic [20] and laser ranging [21] sensors for measuring the fill level. They support long-range communication provided by LoRa [22].
- A LoRa Gateway [23]
- A fog environment at KLEEMANN that acts as LoRa server
- A cloud server that connects to KLEEMANN server to receive fill level data. The server also hosts the data analytics and monitoring platform [16]
- A PC available at ELDIA premises to connect to analytics and monitoring platform
- Networking devices (WiFi Routers) available at KLEEMANN, ELDIA and cloud

In addition to the IoT devices mentioned above, software applications are available such as data analytics and monitoring applications. Moreover, the EFPF Data Spine [24] was used to provide integration, interoperability, and secure communication functionalities between the KLEEMANN factory server and the cloud.

Therefore, a series of potential security threats and risks should be considered.

B. SRM Application

The following steps are followed to develop a system model for the KLEEMANN and ELDIA use case:

Identification of Key Components

The first step in creating the system model is to identify and categorize the essential elements of the system. These include:

- **Networks:** Communication pathways and infrastructure.
- **Computers:** Hardware and computing resources.

- **Processes:** Operational workflows and procedures.
- **Data:** Information assets and data flows.
- **Operators/Users:** Individuals or entities that interact with the system.
- **Physical and Legal Spaces:** Locations and jurisdictional boundaries relevant to the system.

Selection of Relevant Asset Types from the SRM Asset Palette

Once the components are identified, the relevant asset types are selected from the **SRM Asset Palette**. These assets are defined in alignment with the **ISO 27005** standard, ensuring a structured and standardized approach to risk management and system modeling.

Building the System Model

The final step involves building the system model by interconnecting the identified assets. This interconnected model provides a holistic view of the system, enabling a clear understanding of relationships, dependencies, and potential risks.

The system modeling is done using the following three layers:

- The Application Layer (data and processes) – Data, Process
- The Network Layer (sensors, IOT, devices and network connections) - Network Asset
- The Physical Layer (spaces, places and people) – Governance Asset, Space, Stakeholder

Once the assets are identified, we need to connect them with a relationship which is represented as a link in the system model. Application processes that execute software processes in real time are also assets of the system model.

The important part of the risk modeling that is covered by SRM is to model human interactions with the system. Humans can be phished, intentionally or accidentally, compromising the security of the system. To model human interaction in a trustworthy environment, the user "ADULT (legally competent to give their consent for any processing)" is added. ELDIA Planning Manager is added for ELDIA infrastructure and system admin is added for KLEEMANN factory.

Next, hosts and logical subnets are added to model the connectivity of the network layer. The user of the system will need access to it through some interface (e.g. laptop) and connect to the Internet (public network) through a router (logical subnet). The router also provides a wired Local Area Network (LAN) that is connected to the server.

For the KLEEMANN and ELDIA use case, the EFPF/COMPOSITION LoRa Gateway, KLEEMANN WiredLAN, and KLEEMANN Router are added for the KLEEMANN network. The ELDIA router, ELDIA WiredLan, is added to the ELDIA network.

EFPF Data Spine enabled data integration from the KLEEMANN server to the cloud server with analytics and monitoring applications. Data Spine uses the MQTT protocol for communication and Apache NiFi [30] to enable data integration.

tified for the KLEEMANN and ELIDA use-case. Primary threats are caused by direct causes, such as system failure and malicious activity. However, secondary threats occur due to the propagation of primary threats through the system. SRM automatically identifies primary and secondary threats and their consequences on an individual asset. Threats cause consequences in assets and make an interlinked chain of threat-consequence-threat, demonstrating the propagation of security attacks through the system.

When a threat and consequence occur, there will be a negative impact on an individual asset. SSM assigned a default impact level for each asset, as depicted in Fig. 7. The user can change the level of impact to reduce the likelihood of a threat occurring.

Threats can be reduced by implementing some basic controls, such as software patching and security training. SRM provides a list of controls to the security expert, who can then implement these controls to mitigate security risks.

In the current scenario, threats are checked one by one in order to define if they have been removed by security procedures followed from KLEEMANN and ELDIA related to shop-floor installations and from software application providers, regarding the parts of the solutions that are using cloud services and applications such as the Data Spine and the analytics platform. Most of the threats were already solved by technical partners involved in the solutions; some other threats were ignored and considered as 'false positive', and some others were taken into account by IT departments.

Regarding the usability of the tool and the level of modeling that it enables, both KLEEMANN and ELDIA users have evaluated it. The tool interface was evaluated as user-friendly as it allowed for the easy creation of models of various systems. Furthermore, the level of modeling that can provide was defined as well accepted by the KLEEMANN IT staff that has been working on the setup of the real-world system. All the necessary means and components used to set up the system could be modeled using the available assets provided by the SRM tool. A large variety of network assets (network types, routers, controllers, devices, sensors, etc.), hosted assets (data, DBs, web clients, etc.), spaces (public, private), and stakeholders (adults, organizations, etc.) are available by the solution and enables a detailed modeling of the actual system.

The second part of the user evaluation focused on the definition of risk and the threats detected by the tool. Once the modeling phase is completed, the risk analysis procedure begins. This process involves input from end users on the presence of some basic controls or their plans to implement the controls suggested by SRM. After the relevant controls are identified and implemented, a risk analysis is performed. This step helps to mitigate or resolve some of the initial detected threats.

SRM generates a risk treatment plan that outlines the possible consequences for each asset, the associated threats, and how the selected treatment methods and applied controls impact them. This report is available to stakeholders. An example report for the asset "Web Monitoring App" is shown

Threat	Asset	Likelihood	System Risk
Privileged network path(s) from "Web Monitoring App" to "EFPF Data Spine" are open (293a)	[OpenClientServiceAttackPath: Internet-(Web Monitoring App)-(EFPF Data Spine)]	Very High	Medium
Compromised service "EFPF Data Spine" prevents access by "Monitoring and Analytics app" (d6f3)	[ClientServiceRelationship: (Monitoring and Analytics app)-(EFPF Data Spine)]	Very High	Medium
Compromised service "EFPF Data Spine" prevents access by "Web Monitoring App" (74c1)	[ClientServiceRelationship: (Web Monitoring App)-(EFPF Data Spine)]	Very High	Medium
Communication failure between "Monitoring and Analytics app" and "EFPF Data Spine" (17cf)	[ClientServiceRelationship: (Monitoring and Analytics app)-(EFPF Data Spine)]	Very High	Medium
Communication failure between "Web Monitoring App" and "EFPF Data Spine" (b59d)	[ClientServiceRelationship: (Web Monitoring App)-(EFPF Data Spine)]	Very High	Medium
Network access to service "EFPF Data Spine" as "Web Monitoring App" from "EFPF WiredLAN" (839b)	[ClientServiceRelationship: (Web Monitoring App)-(EFPF Data Spine)]	Very High	Medium
Network access to service "EFPF Data Spine" as "Web Monitoring App" from "ELDIA WiredLAN" (3525)	[ClientServiceRelationship: (Web Monitoring App)-(EFPF Data Spine)]	Very High	Medium
Network access to service "EFPF Data Spine" as "Web Monitoring App" from "Internet" (753d)	[ClientServiceRelationship: (Web Monitoring App)-(EFPF Data Spine)]	Very High	Medium
Compromised client "Web Monitoring App" on host "ELDIA PC" used to access "EFPF Data Spine" via "ELDIA WiredLAN" (f381)	[ClientServiceRelationship: (Web Monitoring App)-(EFPF Data Spine)]	Very High	Medium

Fig. 6. Threats

Consequence	Asset	Direct Impact	Likelihood	Direct Risk
LossOfTimeliness	ELDIA Planning Man...	Low	Very High	Medium
LossOfReliability	ELDIA Planning Man...	Low	Medium	Low
CommsSnooperable	EFPF WiredLAN	Negligible	Negligible	Very Low
CommsSnooperable	ELDIA WiredLAN	Negligible	Negligible	Very Low
CommsSnooperable	Internet	Negligible	Negligible	Very Low
CommsSnooperable	KLEEMANN WiredLAN	Negligible	Negligible	Very Low
Loss Of Control	EFPF Server	Negligible	Very High	Very Low
Loss Of Control	EFPF Router	Negligible	Very High	Very Low
Loss Of Control	EFPF/COMPOSITIO...	Negligible	Very High	Very Low
Loss Of Control	Fill Level Sensors	Negligible	Negligible	Very Low

Fig. 7. Consequences and Impact

Consequence	Threats	Treatment Method	Status	Target Date	Controls
Loss of Control	• Insider attack to control "Web Monitoring App"	Mitigate	In Place	n/a	• Screening at ELDIA Planning Manager
Loss of Reliability	• Software bug (reliability) at process "Web Monitoring App"	Mitigate	In Place	n/a	• SoftwarePatching at ELDIA PC
Loss of Availability	• Malicious control of process "Web Monitoring App" • Security implementation issue for data "Analytics and Monitoring Data" • Software bug (crash) at process "Web Monitoring App" • Effect of overload at process "Web Monitoring App"	Mitigate	In Place	n/a	• HealthMonitoring at ELDIA PC • Encryption at Analytics and Monitoring Data • AccessKey at Web Monitoring App • KeyManagement at Web Monitoring App • SoftwarePatching at ELDIA PC
Loss of Availability	• Secondary threat to availability of "Web Monitoring App" due to absent user	Ignore	n/a	n/a	
Overloaded	• Software bug overloads process "Web Monitoring App"	Mitigate	In Place	n/a	• SoftwarePatching at ELDIA PC

Fig. 8. Report of threat handling process

in Fig. 8.

This analysis was regarded highly useful, detailed, and concrete. The tool effectively defined threats and risks, identified their root causes, assessed their likelihood, and classified their risk levels (very high, high, medium, low, very low). In addition, it evaluated the potential effects of each threat. A particularly valuable feature was the control strategies provided by the tool, which support users in mitigating risks and threats.

The SRM was considered to meet the needs of this user story and demonstrated significant potential for application in other systems within the two companies, offering both system modeling and risk analysis capabilities.

In general, stakeholders from both companies agreed that SRM:

- Improves cybersecurity processes and enables the identification of risks in data sharing scenarios such as the supply chain

- Offers the opportunity to conduct advanced risk assessments in a user-friendly way
- Protects the functioning of supply chains based on data sharing scenarios by demonstrating the existing complexities and assisting in developing a fast response
- Secures various components that are vital for effective data sharing such as sensors, routers, gateways, servers, scripts and applications.

V. CONCLUSIONS

IoT-driven data-sharing ecosystems have introduced complex security challenges, including unauthorized access, compliance risks, etc. This paper presented the Security Risk Modeler (SRM), a tool designed to systematically assess and mitigate security risks in such environments. By adhering to the ISO 27005 standard, SRM provides a structured methodology to model threats and evaluate the propagation of risks across interconnected assets. The application of SRM in an industrial waste management scenario demonstrated its effectiveness in identifying primary and secondary threats, assessing their likelihood and impact, and recommending mitigation controls. The tool successfully modeled a distributed IoT system involving sensors, fog/cloud infrastructure, and cross-organizational data sharing. Feedback from stakeholders confirmed the user-friendly interface of SRM and its ability to provide detailed and actionable risk insights.

To further validate these results, additional studies are needed to be conducted in the future along with further experimentation. The SRM tool is planned to be applied in some more complex scenarios for modeling the risks of use cases coming from a Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC) that provides a challenging Cloud-Edge infrastructure.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the European Union's "Horizon Europe" Programme Under Grant Agreement No 101135423 - ENACT project. Furthermore, we thank KLEEMANN Hellas and ELDIA representatives for supporting the testing and validation activities in the current study.

REFERENCES

- [1] Xu, X., Lu, Y., Vogel-Heuser, B., & Wang, L. (2021). "Industry 4.0 and Industry 5.0—Inception, conception and perception." *Journal of manufacturing systems*, 61, 530-535.
- [2] Khanna, A., & Kaur, S. (2020). "Internet of things (IoT), applications and challenges: a comprehensive review." *Wireless Personal Communications*, 114, 1687-1762.
- [3] Alani, M. M., & Alloghani, M. (2019). "Security challenges in the industry 4.0 era." *Industry 4.0 and engineering for a sustainable future*, 117-136.
- [4] Supriya, S., & Padaki, S. (2016, December). "Data security and privacy challenges in adopting solutions for IOT." In *2016 IEEE International Conference on Internet of Things (iThings) and IEEE Green Computing and Communications (GreenCom) and IEEE Cyber, Physical and Social Computing (CPSCom) and IEEE Smart Data (SmartData)* (pp. 410-415). IEEE.
- [5] Altulaihian, E., Almaiah, M. A., & Aljughaiman, A. (2022). Cybersecurity threats, countermeasures and mitigation techniques on the IoT: Future research directions. *Electronics*, 11(20), 3330.

- [6] Hussain, S., Kamal, A., Ahmad, S., Rasool, G., Iqbal, S.: Threat modelling methodologies: a survey. *Sci. Int.(Lahore)* 26(4), 1607–1609 (2014)
- [7] Jbair, M., Ahmad, B., Maple, C., & Harrison, R. (2022). Threat modelling for industrial cyber physical systems in the era of smart manufacturing. *Computers in Industry*, 137, 103611.
- [8] Singh, K., Kumar, B.: A stride-based secure framework for software-defined net- working. In: 2024 2nd International Conference on Cyber Resilience (ICCR), pp. 1–6 (2024).
- [9] McRee, R.: Microsoft threat modeling tool 2014: identify & mitigate. *ISSA Journal* 39, 42 (2014)
- [10] Ansari, M.T.J., Pandey, D., Alenezi, M.: Store: Security threat oriented require- ments engineering methodology. *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences* 34(2), 191–203 (2022)
- [11] Zhang, L., Taal, A., Cushing, R., Laat, C., Grosso, P.: A risk-level assessment system based on the stride/dread model for digital data marketplaces. *International Journal of Information Security*, 1–17 (2022)
- [12] Xiong, W., Legrand, E., Åberg, O., & Lagerström, R. (2022). Cyber security threat modeling based on the MITRE Enterprise ATT&CK Matrix. *Software and Systems Modeling*, 21(1), 157-177.
- [13] Phillips, S.C., Taylor, S., Boniface, M., Modafferi, S., Surridge, M.: Automated knowledge-based cybersecurity risk assessment of cyber-physical systems. *IEEE Access* (2024)
- [14] ISO/IEC 27005:2022 - Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Guidance on managing information security risks <https://www.iso.org/standard/80585.html>
- [15] Nizamis, A., Neises, J., Ospina, D., Wajid, U., López, C. I. V., Trakadas, P., ... & Palau, C. (2024, June). ENACT-A Framework for Adaptive Scheduling and Deployments of Data Intensive Workloads on Energy Efficient Edge to Cloud Continuum. In 2024 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation (ICE/ITMC) (pp. 1-9). IEEE.
- [16] Vafeiadis, T., Nizamis, A., Pavlopoulos, V., Giugliano, L., Rousopoulou, V., Ioannidis, D., & Tzovaras, D. (2019, May). Data analytics platform for the optimization of waste management procedures. In 2019 15th International Conference on Distributed Computing in Sensor Systems (DCOSS) (pp. 333-338). IEEE.
- [17] Mastos, T. D., Nizamis, A., Vafeiadis, T., Alexopoulos, N., Ntinis, C., Gkortzis, D., ... & Tzovaras, D. (2020). Industry 4.0 sustainable supply chains: An application of an IoT enabled scrap metal management solution. *Journal of cleaner production*, 269, 122377.
- [18] KLEEMANN Hellas S.A.: <https://kleemannlifts.com/> (2025)
- [19] ELDIA S.A.: <https://eldia.gr/eteria/?lang=en> (2025)
- [20] MB7380 Ultrasonic sensor: <https://www.nex-robotics.com/products/sensors/ultrasonic-range-sensors/hrxl-maxsonar-wr-series/ultrasonic-range-finder-hrxlwr-wrt-mb7380.html> (2025)
- [21] VL53L0X Time-of-Flight (ToF) laser-ranging: <https://www.st.com/en/imaging-and-photonics-solutions/vl53l0x.html> (2025)
- [22] LoRa: <https://www.thethingsnetwork.org/docs/lorawan/what-is-lorawan/> (2025)
- [23] LoRa Gateway - LoRaWAN: <https://webshop.ideetron.nl/LORANK-8-OEM?Product=202128253&Lng=en> (2025)
- [24] Deshmukh, R. A., Jayakody, D., Schneider, A., & Damjanovic-Behrendt, V. (2021). Data spine: a federated interoperability enabler for heterogeneous IoT platform ecosystems. *Sensors*, 21(12), 4010.
- [25] ISO/IEC 27005:2022 - Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Guidance on managing information security risks: <https://www.iso.org/standard/80585.html>
- [26] ISO/IEC 27001:2022 - Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security management systems — Requirements: <https://www.iso.org/standard/27001>
- [27] KeyCloak Open Source Identity and Access Management Framework: <https://www.keycloak.org/>
- [28] MongoDB - The World's Leading Modern Database: <https://www.mongodb.com/>
- [29] Apache Jena TDB - A high performance RDF store: <https://jena.apache.org/documentation/tdb/>
- [30] Apache NiFi to automate the flow of data between software systems: <https://nifi.apache.org/>
- [31] ISO, ISO/IEC 27005:2022. ISO. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/80585.html> (accessed Apr. 7, 2025).
- [32] OWASP Foundation, *The Open Source Foundation for Application Security — OWASP Foundation*. Available: https://owasp.org/?gclid=Cj0KCQjwpPKiBhDvARIsACn-gzCo7UCFJDU8s9R6CPl-hk6x8m7_-AjOV2g3eSJv9Bonb98szPF1dz4aAjy6EALw_wcB (accessed Apr. 7, 2025).
- [33] *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) – Official Legal Text*, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Available: <https://gdpr-info.eu/> (accessed Apr. 7, 2025).